

Section 1: Applicants

Name of the main applicant	Dr. ir. Hakim Achterberg
Affiliation – institution	Erasmus MC
Affiliation – department	Radiology & Nuclear Medicine
Position	Senior research software engineer
End date of contract	██████████
Guarantee needed & added yes/no/n.a.	█
E-mail address	██████████
ORCID ID	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3772-4582

Name of the co-applicant	Ing. Adriaan Versteeg
Affiliation – institution	Erasmus MC
Affiliation – department	Radiology & Nuclear Medicine
Position	Senior research software engineer
End date of contract	██████████
Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	█
E-mail address	██████████
ORCID ID	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1375-7873

Name of the co-applicant	Dr. Ir. Stefan Klein
Affiliation – institution	Erasmus MC
Affiliation – department	Radiology & Nuclear Medicine
Position	Associate Professor
Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	█
End date of contract	██████████
E-mail address	██████████
ORCID ID	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4449-6784

Name of the co-applicant	Dr. E. E. Bron
Affiliation – institution	Erasmus MC
Affiliation – department	Radiology & Nuclear Medicine
Position	Assistant Professor
Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	█
End date of contract	██████████
E-mail address	██████████
ORCID ID	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5778-9263

Name of the cooperation partner (person)	dr. Simon Doran
E-mail address	[REDACTED]
Organisation	The Institute of Cancer Research

Section 2: Summary

Proposed project title	Medical Imaging Curation and Annotation Platform
Project duration (in months)	24 months

English public summary

The proposed project aims to create a medical imaging annotation platform aligned with the FAIR and open science principles, improving data standardization, interoperability, and accessibility. By incorporating an integrated Standard Operating Procedure for annotation, the platform will reduce human error, lower the administrative burden, and minimize inter-observer bias. Built on open-source software, it will support interoperability with Health-RI infrastructure, enabling seamless data integration and re-use. The platform will include image annotation tools, standardized templates, task lists, and automatic data management. Planned training, open-source licensing, and community engagement ensure broad adoption and long-term usability in medical research.

Word count EN-SUM (max 100): 96

Dutch public summary

Het voorgestelde project omvat de ontwikkeling van een medisch beeldannotatieplatform volgens FAIR- en open science-principes, met verbeterde standaardisatie, interoperabiliteit en toegankelijkheid. Een geïntegreerde standaardwerkwijze vermindert menselijke fouten, administratieve lasten en beoordelaarsvariatie. Het platform, gebaseerd op open-source software, ondersteunt interoperabiliteit met Health-RI voor soepele data-integratie en hergebruik. Het biedt annotatietools, gestandaardiseerde sjablonen, takenlijsten en automatische gegevensbeheer. Training, open-source licenties en betrokkenheid van de gemeenschap bevorderen brede adoptie en langdurig beschikbaarheid voor medisch onderzoek.

Word count NL-SUM (max 100): 72

Section 3: Alignment with the scope of the call

3.1 Vision for the project and alignment with the aim of this call

Annotated data is the new currency in the age of artificial intelligence (AI). We envision a framework for annotation of medical images that allows data holders to define a standard operating procedure (SOP), which the framework will then guide and enforce. The system will present the annotator with all the data and the matching annotation input forms/tools. Furthermore, the SOP will define the standard layout of the viewer, ensuring that all annotators are guided through the annotation process in a similar fashion. Once the annotation is finished, the resulting data will be automatically stored in the appropriate location. This way, administrative burden and the room for human errors are lowered, leading to more efficient annotation with less risk of error. The annotation framework will be offered as a web-based platform to end-users, allowing easy use by clinicians and researchers, and thus enabling the creation of [FAIR](#) and annotated datasets.

Word count SEC31 (max. 150): 149

3.2 User communities, challenges and needs

Data is vital in medical research as it serves as the foundation for advancing our understanding of diseases, treatment and outcomes. With epidemiological studies or Artificial Intelligence (AI) research we can make predictions and aid in clinical decision making. In medical imaging research, data is used for the development and validation of innovative imaging techniques and diagnostic tools. High-quality datasets enable researchers to train algorithms, improve image processing methods, and enhance the accuracy of diagnostic models. Furthermore, high quality data improves the quality of medical research and AI development, empowering data-driven prediction and decision making.

In most current medical imaging studies, the collection and annotation of the imaging data is not standardised. Usually, annotators open a medical scan in the viewer of their choice and register annotations in a Case Report Form (CRF), Excel file, or as separate files. This potentially leads to data mismatch through human error and lacks standardisation of the viewer (settings). A structured, integrated solution, implementing a SOP, makes such data mismatch errors impossible and leads to more harmonised data. Additionally, there will be lower administrative burden on the annotators as they can focus solely on the annotation task.

Word count SEC32 (max. 200): 196

3.3 Alignment of project with OS principles

By formalising the SOP and having an integrated annotation framework, the system can trace the provenance of the data annotation. In this way, metadata for the annotations is automatically generated, enabling a correct description of the data and making it more suitable for re-use. Additionally, by using open standards (e.g., DICOM, HL7) for data import and export, the system and resulting data will be more interoperable. This project will therefore contribute to the implementation of the FAIR and open science principles.

Previously, we have created viewers with annotation capabilities based on the [MeVisLab](#) framework. However, their licensing, which has gotten more restrictive over time, renders this path unsustainable. We recognise the importance of open science and sustainability of science infrastructure. Therefore, we will make sure the proposed medical image annotation framework will be created built on open-source libraries (e.g., the Open Health Imaging Foundation (OHIF) viewer, Ziegler et al. 2020). Furthermore, to ensure wide usability we will use an open governance structure, actively including the community in defining the roadmap and providing feedback. Additionally, the solution will be designed to be compatible with the national [Health-RI](#) medical imaging infrastructure, making it a natural extension to it.

Word count SEC33 (max. 200): 196

Section 4: Feasibility

4.1 Project plan

We propose to build a platform that implements the framework as envisioned above. This means there are several elements that the platform should support:

1. The platform integrates medical imaging viewing capabilities with annotation options. These include both image annotation tools (e.g., markers, contours, brush, rulers) as well as electronic case report forms (eCRF). These eCRFs allow to add data (e.g., checkboxes, free text) linked directly to the image.
2. The platform will support templates to control the layout of the viewer as well as the annotations to be performed. This will present all annotators with the same optimal viewer for each task. The choice for the templates used in a study can in turn be formalized in an SOP.
3. The platform will support task lists. The tasks will be loaded from a task list and presented as a worklist to annotators. This will allow them to simply start from the first task and click next to move forward or pick a specific task if desired.
4. The platform will load and save all data for a task automatically, depending on the task definition. This eliminates the possibility of mismatching annotations or eCRF data with the wrong imaging data.
5. The platform will be able to connect to the national Health-RI infrastructure and [the Cancer Imaging Europe \(EUCAIM, Martí-Bonmatí et al. 2025\)](#) infrastructure, meaning that the standards and systems used by Health-RI and EUCAIM (e.g., XNAT for medical imaging storage, Marcus et al. 2007) will be supported.

Figure 1: Mock-up of annotator workflow

Figure 1 illustrates the workflow of an annotator using the platform. First annotators, sign in to the platform via a web browser. Once signed in, they will be presented with the list of tasks assigned to them. These can be filtered based on status or other fields. The annotator can then either select a specific task or simply click a button for the next open task. This will then open the annotation task, which automatically sets up the interface and loads the correct data for this task. Once the annotations are finished, the annotator can either go back to the task overview or simply click 'next task'; in either case the annotations will be saved in the correct place automatically. This allows annotators to experience a focussed annotation workflow, where they do not need to think about the administrative parts at all. But if they need to check or expedite specific tasks, the task overview gives them the option to do so.

To create the platform and the underlying framework, a medical image viewer with integrated annotation capabilities as described above must be created. We will develop this software using a solid software development process according to the following software development lifecycle:

- Requirements engineering; create a list of requirements for the platform based on user surveys.
- Design of the integrated viewer, based on the requirements and specifications defined above.
- Implementation of the design.
- Validation of the platform: perform tests to verify that the requirements are met.
- Documentation: Ensure there is solid documentation both for users that want to annotate data with the platform and system administrators that want to deploy/install the platform.

To enable the community to provide feedback and ensure the platform reflects their needs, we plan to send out surveys in the Health-RI and XNAT communities we are part of, as well as among clinical researchers and technicians in our own institute that perform annotation tasks for their work. We will establish a User Panel that can propose use cases, propose ideas, and give feedback on the requirements and design in various stages of development. Additionally, we will keep the requirements, design, roadmap, code, and issue trackers open from start to finish and the team will make sure to respond to feedback and issues in a timely manner, to give the community confidence that their input is valued.

Figure 2: Release strategy

To make the platform easily accessible and usable by the medical imaging community, we will create extra training and onboarding materials to get users started. We will use a tiered release strategy (see Figure 2). First, we test the platform with internal use case(s) to ensure the desired quality. Next, we will present the platform at a Health-RI imaging community meeting and setup a support structure. Finally, we will give training sessions on other conferences/meetings and promote use in international settings. To ensure that the platform can be used by everyone, we will provide a simple deployment method with solid documentation.

Word count SEC41 (max. 750): 749

4.2 Team composition

Name, surname	Affiliation	Expertise	Role/contributions
Dr. Ir. Hakim Achterberg	Erasmus MC	Research Software Engineer, Medical Imaging Infrastructure	Project manager, Lead Software developer
Ing. Adriaan Versteeg	Erasmus MC	Research Software Engineer, Medical Imaging Infrastructure	Software developer
Dr. Ir. Stefan Klein	Erasmus MC	Associate Professor Medical Imaging	Use cases and user feedback
Dr. Esther Bron	Erasmus MC	Assistant Professor Neuroimage Analysis	Use cases and user feedback
To be hired	Erasmus MC	Front-end developer, Javascript	Software developer
Dr. Simon Doran	Institute of Cancer research	XNAT and OHIF viewer	Cooperation partner, development of framework for federated annotation

Within the department of Radiology and Nuclear Medicine, a team of research software engineers develops infrastructure for medical imaging research for studies like the [Rotterdam Study](#), [MRCLEAN](#), [H2020-EuCanImage.eu](#), [Digital Europe-EUCAIM](#). Additionally, the team has set up and maintains the central imaging archive (XNAT) for the national Health-RI infrastructure. They are also active in [Euro-Biolmaging](#) as the [population imaging flagship node](#).

Hakim Achterberg obtained his PhD in medical image analysis and continued as a research software engineer. He developed software for an infrastructure for imaging studies, including viewer and annotation software for the Rotterdam Study and Heart-Brain Connection. He developed [XNATpy](#), an open-source client library for XNAT written in Python, used in many institutes world-wide including all Dutch University Medical Centers, Washington University, UCL, Oxford University, and the [Australian Imaging Service](#).

Adriaan Versteeg is a senior research software engineer at the Erasmus MC. He has successfully implemented several prototype clinical workstations that include viewing and annotation components, for example for the EASE application for clinical implementation of automated tumour segmentation (van Garderen et al., 2021)

Stefan Klein and Esther Bron have extensive experience in medical imaging research. Their groups often require annotated data and as such they will provide us with the first use cases to test the platform.

We will collaborate with the Institute of Cancer Research (ICR), where the group of Dr. Doran is interested in adding functionality to make the platform work for federated studies, where the data to be annotated is in different storage systems. Their team created the original XNAT OHIF viewer plugin.

Word count SEC42 (max. 350): 350

4.3 Risk management

Risk	Likelihood and impact	Risk mitigation strategy
Underlying libraries change licensing	Likelihood: low Impact: medium	New version of the library can't be used, but the last version can be forked. Additionally, main dependencies will be screened for a strong and thriving open-source community.
Changes in the storage services used in the field	Likelihood: medium Impact: medium	By using open standards and a plugin infrastructure to connect to the data services, we can easily support multiple data sources and adapt to new storage back-ends in case of changes.
Low community uptake and support	Likelihood: medium Impact: high	By including the community early in the project, at the requirements stage already, we will make sure the platform will serve the community's needs. When the tool is developed, we will present it in the community and deliver training materials for onboarding.

Word count SEC43 (max. 150): 138

4.4 Budget

Position	HOT scale	Institu- tion	Total FTE	Years active	Amount
Junior Research Software Engineer		Erasmu	2,00	2	
Senior Research Software Engineer		Erasmu	0,50	2	

Material/IT Type	Description	Cost calculation	Total (€)
(international) travel and accommodation expenses incl. conference visit	Conferences to present the platform for outreach to potential user, e.g. ECR, ESMRMB	3 visits for 2 persons x 1500 euros	€ 9.000,00
Hardware	Hosting a demo instance for testing purposes and training sessions	(Virtual) machine for hosting a demo/training/testing instance	€ 3.000,00
knowledge dissemination costs	Create website, branding, posters, handouts	Design and print posters/handouts to use during outreach events	€ 2.500,00
national symposium/conference/workshop organised by	Host a workshop to present and	Catering for 1 day for	€ 2.000,00

Total Personnel requested: €226.285,00

Total Material/IT requested: €16.500,00

Total budget requested: €242.785,00

4.5 Budget justification

The main cost for the project will be the personnel to create the software for the medical imaging curation and annotation platform. To this end we propose to hire a full-time research software engineer that will do most of the development, especially, the work on the user interface of the platform. To support this junior engineer, we plan to reserve time from our senior research software engineers to support the newly hired junior. Our current engineers have a very strong knowledge of the infrastructure and back-end. We reserved a bit more time in the first year to help the junior get started efficiently.

Besides personnel costs, we request budget for material costs related to dissemination/outreach: 1) Attending international conferences to present the new platform; 2) Hardware for hosting a demo instance for new users (not a production infrastructure but a pre-populated demo instance); 3) A budget for creating branding for the platform, e.g. website, posters, and handouts to increase visibility and support other outreach; and 4) organisation of a workshop to train (potential) users to use to platform. These are all efforts to increase usage and sustainability of the platform.

Word count SEC 45 (max. 200): 190

4.6 Impact plan

This proposal will lead to a readily available medical imaging curation and annotation platform that allows studies using medical images to easily organise structured annotation workflows. The platform will make medical image annotation simpler and lead to more FAIR results, improving both the availability and quality of annotated datasets. This will help unlocking the value of medical images, as high-quality curation and annotation are paramount to using them effectively. Note that the creation of automated annotation methods relies heavily on high quality manual annotations. To maximise impact, we will promote the platform and integrate it in (inter)national infrastructures via Health-RI, EUCAIM, and Euro-Biolmaging.

There is also a need from industry to use annotated medical imaging from hospitals, to develop and evaluate their software for image analysis. The recently established European Health Data Space (EHDS, Slokenberga 2025) regulation promotes such secondary use of hospital data for research and innovation, via a secure processing environment that prohibits data download. However, industry often requires specific annotations, and creating those annotations is a

time-consuming and expensive process. Our platform can help streamline the annotation process and thus facilitate the collaboration with industry on the development of new commercial products certified for clinical use.

Word count SEC46 (max. 200): 199

Section 5: Sustainability and software management

Section 5.1: Sustainability plan

Our sustainability plan consists of various iterative steps from local deployment to global open-source deployment and community involvement. First, we plan to implement the proposed viewing and annotation platform in our own institute and projects we are directly involved in. This will support large prospective population studies such as the Rotterdam Study and research projects that aim at development and validation of AI based on large amounts of retrospective data, such as the [Liver Artificial Intelligence project](#)[Liver Artificial Intelligence project](#).

Second, we will create business activities around the platform which supports maintenance of the software and platform. The [Erasmus MC Imaging Office](#)[Erasmus MC Imaging Office](#) offers imaging services for projects that do not have the expertise themselves. The Imaging Office serves researchers in the Erasmus MC, as well as (inter)national researchers through Health-RI and Euro-BioImaging. At the [Institute of Cancer Research](#)², Dr. Doran's group has a long-established (5+ years) sustainable business model for XNAT medical image analysis with a wide range of related services. Both these groups will offer services based on the curation and annotation platform; this will generate the needed funds through project collaborations and paid services, to maintain and innovate the platform after this project ends.

Finally, we will incorporate the created software/platform in inter(national) infrastructures we are involved in. This includes the Dutch national [Health-RI](#)[Health-RI](#) and the [EUCAIM](#)² projects that aims to create a pan-European federated infrastructure for cancer images. This will ensure the curation and annotation platform will become an integral part of the international imaging infrastructure. Additionally, we will present the platform internationally and provide training workshops to improve community uptake. The open-source nature of the project will enable other users to implement the tool at their institute, fix bugs, and add new features.

Word count SEC51 (max 300): 284

Section 5.2: Software management plan

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended audience.

The software is a web-based medical image annotation and curation platform. It provides a task-based annotation workflow and can connect to imaging data stored in databases such as XNAT or a PACS system. It can be used by researchers, technicians, or clinicians to create annotations for medical images.

2. How will you manage versioning of your software?

We will use [git](#) as the version control system to manage the code base. We will use the [GitFlow](#) branching model to keep a stable master branch, while developing new features. Versions will be tagged in the repository and releases will be created. For these versions Docker images will be built and supplied for easy deployment.

3. How will you make your software publicly available? What licence will your software have?

The software will be open-source and licensed under the Apache 2.0 license. The code will be hosted publicly on GitLab. The releases will be published as Docker containers, accompanied by helm charts and Docker compose files. Python packages will be released at the [Python Package Index](#).

To increase the visibility of the platform we will register the software in tool repositories such as [bio.tools](#) and the [Research Software Directory](#).

4. How will users of your software be able to cite your software?

We will generate an [Zenodo](#) entry to provide a DOI and reference for the software. This will allow people to reference the software in general or a specific version of the software.

5. How will your software be documented? Please describe your plans for: user documentation, documentation for future developers and for installation requirements. Please provide links to documentation if already available.

We will create user documentation that describes the usage of the tool. Additionally, we will create a deployment and development documentation that describes how to host your own instance of the platform and how to start with development. The user documentation will be hosted at an online public platform such as [ReadTheDocs](#). The deployment and development documentation could be hosted at the same platform or at a Gitlab wiki connected to the code repository.

6. How will contribution guidelines and governance structure of your software be documented?

A file in the repository root for code of conduct and contributing will be added in which guidelines will be documented in the Markdown format.

7. How will your software be tested?

The software will be tested using automated testing in the form of unit, functional, and integration tests. For acceptance testing this will be complemented by a test plan that might also include manual user testing. The automated tests will be included in the CI/CD pipeline on GitLab so they will automatically run on events like pushed code, merge requests, and releases.

8. How will you check that it respects the licences of libraries and dependencies it uses?

As part of the CI/CD pipeline for creating releases, we will perform a license scan that will check the licenses for the dependencies and check the compatibility with our license.

9. How will your software be packaged and distributed?

When releasing the software, we will create a release on GitLab and create a tag in the VCS. Then a CI/CD will build Docker containers and provide a Docker-Compose file for easy deployment of the platform. Additionally, we will provide helm charts for deploying the platform on a [Kubernetes](#) cluster.

10. What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organised?

The software will be supplied with online user documentation. There will be an issue tracker in the Gitlab repository where people can report bugs or request features. Additionally, we will work towards making the platform an official part of the national Health-RI infrastructure so we can leverage the Health-RI service desk and training facilities for end-user support.

11. How do you plan to ensure long term maintenance of your software?

The software will be developed as a collaboration with others in the Health-RI and XNAT communities. The Erasmus MC Imaging Office will offer services and data based on the curation and annotation platform, which will guarantee

Open Science Infrastructure 2024 full proposal - Small

that there will be support for maintaining the service. Additionally, we are in contact with the ICR (Dr. Simon Doran) who need a similar curation and annotation platform and agreed to co-develop. The ICR and Royal Marsden Hospital have a business model to support XNAT services, and they would like to include the annotation platform in their portfolio. By including the software in service offerings, there is a long-term support and maintenance guaranteed. Large features can be added when they are required for specific projects that have budget for that purpose.

Section 6: References

van Garderen KA, van der Voort SR, Versteeg A, Koek M, Gutierrez A, van Straten M, Rentmeester M, Klein S and Smits M (2021) EASE: Clinical Implementation of Automated Tumor Segmentation and Volume Quantification for Adult Low-Grade Glioma. *Front. Med.* 8:738425. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2021.738425>

Marcus, D. S., Olsen, T. R., Ramaratnam, M., & Buckner, R. L. (2007). The Extensible Neuroimaging Archive Toolkit: an informatics platform for managing, exploring, and sharing neuroimaging data. *Neuroinformatics*, 5(1), 11–34. <https://doi.org/10.1385/ni:5:1:11>

Martí-Bonmatí, L., Blanquer, I., Tsiknakis, M., Tsakou, G., Martinez, R., Capella-Gutierrez, S., Zullino, S., Meszaros, J., Bron, E. E., Gelpi, J. L., Riklund, K., Chaabane, L., Schlemmer, H. P., Aznar, M., Serrano Candelas, P., Gordebeke, P., Hierath, M., EUCAIM Consortium, & European Society of Radiology (2025). Empowering cancer research in Europe: the EUCAIM cancer imaging infrastructure. *Insights into imaging*, 16(1), 47. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13244-025-01913-x>

Slokenberga, S., Ó Cathaoir, K., & Shabani, M. (Eds.). (2025). *The European Health Data Space: Examining A New Era in Data Protection* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003544111>

Ziegler, E., Urban, T., Brown, D., Petts, J., Pieper, S. D., Lewis, R., Hafey, C., & Harris, G. J. (2020). Open Health Imaging Foundation Viewer: An Extensible Open-Source Framework for Building Web-Based Imaging Applications to Support Cancer Research. *JCO clinical cancer informatics*, 4, 336–345. <https://doi.org/10.1200/CCI.19.00131>

Section 7: Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.
- I have submitted a pre-proposal for this Call for proposals in ISAAC.